

On the Investigation of a Sustainable Two Step Laser-Based Surface Treatment for the Functionalization of Additive Manufactured Ti–6Al–4V Components

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Additive manufacturing innovates component production in industries like healthcare and aerospace due to its ability to create complex geometries, reduce waste, and enable on-demand manufacturing. Despite its advantages, the fabricated components often present high surface roughness, impacting the mechanical properties and functionality of the parts while also negatively influencing postprocessability, e.g., for functionalizing their surfaces by texturing micro/nano structures. This study presents the development of a two-step process for surface smoothing and microstructuring, combining laser polishing (LP) and direct laser interference patterning (DLIP). Ti–6Al–4V coupons are fabricated with different building orientation angles (BOA) and later polished using a continuous wave laser. Strong influence of the BOA on the initial surface roughness is observed; the LP reduces roughness from 31 μm to $\approx 1.7 \mu\text{m}$. Once the surface is sufficiently smooth, DLIP is used to create line-like microstructures. Structures obtained with nanosecond pulses show higher aspect ratios (≈ 1.0) compared to the fabricated using picosecond pulses (≈ 0.5). In both cases, high homogeneity values are reached ($>85\%$ – 90%). Finally, a new approach for evaluating the performance of the process in terms of energy consumption and structural parameters of the produced patterns is presented, denoting the advantages and disadvantages for each case.

complex geometry production, and waste reduction, have significantly contributed to its market growth and importance. Furthermore, compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 13.9% is expected until 2028 with a revenue generation of 20 billion USD.^[6]

With the continuous evolution of AM methods, improvements in material properties, production speed, and cost-effectiveness are anticipated to drive broader adoption across various industries.^[7] In the aerospace sector, AM is being used for producing lightweight and geometrically optimized parts for enhanced fuel efficiency and reduced launch costs.^[8] In healthcare, these methods enable the production of patient-specific implants, prosthetics, and complex surgical tools.^[9] Among the materials commonly employed, Ti–6Al–4V stands out as the leading Ti-alloy in the market,^[10] spearheading the new developments in healthcare, for example in prosthetics manufacturing,^[11] because of its outstanding mechanical properties^[12] and excellent biocompatibility.^[13,14]

Despite the benefits of AM, this technology presents also challenges, particularly regarding surface quality. Components produced by laser powder bed fusion (LPBF), a popular AM technique which accounts for 40% of equipment sales revenue of the AM segment,^[6] often exhibit high surface roughness that can exceed 10–20 μm .^[13] This effect is related to the nature of powder-based layering and the presence of unmelted or partially melted powder particles.^[2] Such surface

1. Introduction

In recent years, additive manufacturing (AM) has revolutionized the production of complex, high-performance components across various sectors, particularly in healthcare and aerospace.^[1–5] The unique capacity of AM, including on-demand manufacturing,

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irregularities can adversely affect the mechanical properties (e.g., fatigue), corrosion resistance, and overall functionality of the produced parts.^[15,16]

Conventional methods for improving surface quality, generally include mechanical and chemical polishing. For example, Rosa et al. reported that conventional abrasive polishing methods for AM parts are frequently unsuitable for complex geometries due to limited accessibility and the requirement for manual operations, which may also entail risks to operator health. Furthermore, electrochemical processes hold environmental drawbacks due to chemical waste.^[17] Laser-based surface modification techniques represent a convenient alternative to more traditional methods. In the case of laser polishing (LP), localized laser radiation focused on the workpiece is used to remelt a thin layer of material, generating a uniform layer of liquid metal. Then as the metal resolidifies, fewer defects are produced due to the uniform surface tension in the liquid phase, as reported by several authors.^[18,19] Compared with traditional roughness reduction methods, such as mechanical polishing or sandblasting, LP is contactless, avoids abrasive embedding and tool wear while remaining adaptable to complex features, thereby making it particularly suitable for processing AM components.^[20,21] A major limitation of LP is the restricted accessibility of certain surfaces. In particular, internal surfaces or shadowed regions of complex geometries may not be directly reached by the laser beam, which limits the applicability of the process. While part design in LPBF can be adapted to improve accessibility, in cases where shadowed regions cannot be avoided, alternative finishing methods may still be required.

Beyond reducing surface roughness, laser radiation can also be used to impart new functionalities to a surface and thus improve the performance of AM-produced components.^[22,23] This can be achieved for instance, by creating periodic surface structures having feature sizes in the nanometer and/or micrometer ranges. In this frame, laser microfabrication methods such as direct laser writing (DLW) have shown to provide the needed level of flexibility and process speed, allowing the precise tailoring of the surface topography and thus creating new functionalities.^[24] However, DLW is generally disadvantaged by the lateral resolution of the produced features being limited to the diameter of the laser beam at the focal position (typically 15–45 μm).

To produce higher resolution patterns a method called Direct Laser Interference Patterning (DLIP) can be utilized, permitting to produce repetitive structures with feature sizes even below 1 μm . DLIP uses the interference principle to fabricate periodic surface structures by locally ablating or melting the material at interference maxima positions.^[25–27] The application of DLIP in a two-beam configuration to produce line-like structures using pulsed lasers with pulse durations ranging from the femtosecond to the nanosecond regime has been extensively investigated. This approach has been demonstrated to impart novel functionalities to the treated surfaces, including wettability modification, friction reduction, and enhanced cell adhesion, in a single step and without the need for external etching agents.^[28–30] In the case of Ti alloys, the two-beam DLIP configuration has been employed for instance to induce antibacterial properties,^[31] enhance the biocompatibility of implants or improving corrosion resistance.^[32,33]

Further studies regarding the functionalization of conventionally manufactured Ti–6Al–4V parts using different laser-based

methods have been also published in the past years for general biomedical applications.^[34–36]

Concerning the application of laser-based polishing and laser structuring for surface functionalization, a limited amount of research works have been performed.^[37–39] For example, Solheid et al. combined continuous wave LP with femtosecond laser DLW for fabricating “pore-like” structures as well as laser induced periodic surface structures (LIPSS).^[39] In other work, Kuisat et al. employed ns and ps-DLIP combined with DLW on top of AM Ti64 and Scalmalloy in their as-built state to tailor their wettability properties. In addition, when implementing DLIP on AM-fabricated parts, it has been shown that the initial surface roughness can significantly influence the fabrication of homogeneous periodic structures.^[40] Finally, to the best of the authors knowledge, the combination of LP with CW lasers (commonly used for LP) and DLIP treatment using both ns and ps pulses, while simultaneously aiming to achieve high homogeneity and low energy consumption, remains unexplored.

This study focuses on the sustainable development of a two-step process for surface smoothing and microstructuring, combining LP and DLIP laser-based methods. First, Ti–6Al–4V coupons are AM-fabricated with different building orientation angles (BOA). Then the roughness of the AM components is reduced by LP to a level suitable for DLIP. Once the surface is sufficiently smooth, DLIP is used to create microstructures, aiming to reach a high degree of homogeneity. The DLIP method is employed with both ns and ps pulses, producing line-like periodic patterns. A systematic approach is then developed to identify the optimum process window, balancing surface quality as well as laser power consumption, in order to assess the overall performance of the used methods. Although the study does not address specific functional applications, the insights gained will enable the sustainable production of functional 3D parts in future work.

2. Experimental Section

Coupons of Ti–6Al–4V alloy were manufactured by LPBF method, using a DMP flex system (3D Systems, United States) equipped with a 500 W laser in an argon atmosphere. BOA is defined as the angle between the main axis of the fabricated part and the plane of the print bed.^[41] According to their orientation, surfaces can be classified into horizontal (top) surfaces, vertical (side) surfaces, upward-facing surfaces (up-skin), and downward-facing surfaces (down-skin or overhanging surfaces). In this study, samples with BOA of 0°, 30°, 60°, 90°, and 120° were fabricated. Here, the 120° orientation angle corresponds to a down-skin/overhanging surface. Schematics of the print bed where coupon orientation and the coupon faces employed in this study are shown can be found in Figure S1 of supporting information.

Afterward, the AM-produced parts were laser polished using the system shown in **Figure 1a** (3D SYLAS SLEEK 1000, SYLAS, France). The system includes a 1 kW CW laser source with a central wavelength of 980 nm (LDM 1000-30, Laserline, Germany), having a focusing optics resulting in a spot diameter of 0.9 mm. The laser power was varied from 325 to 540 W and the samples were scanned at a fixed speed of 3000 mm/min. The process was

Figure 1. Schematics of a) laser polishing machine approach and b) direct laser interference patterning step for surface functionalization.

performed in a chamber flushed with argon to maintain the internal atmosphere at an oxygen level of 500 ppm.

Next, selected samples were treated using DLIP, with ns or ps laser pulses. The general principle of the DLIP process is schematically depicted in Figure 1b. In case of the ns-pulse treatment, an InnoSlab IS400-3-GH laser source (Edgewave GmbH, Germany) was employed, delivering pulses with a pulse duration of 7 ns and a fundamental wavelength λ of 1064 nm. The used DLIP optical head (ELIPSYS, SurFunction GmbH, Germany) splits the main laser beam into two sub-beams using a diffractive optical element (DOE). These two sub-beams are then shaped and overlapped at the working position using an array of lenses. In this way, an elongated laser spot, containing the interference pattern, with dimensions of $\approx 90 \times 5000 \mu\text{m}$ is produced. The generated line-like interference pattern had a spatial period of 6.0 μm . For treating the metallic samples, the pulse-to-pulse overlap was adjusted from 60% to 99%, and repetition rates of 1.5 and 5 kHz were selected. The laser fluence was adjusted to 2.8 J cm^{-2} and kept constant over the different repetition rates by changing the output power of the laser source.

In case of the ps-DLIP treatment, the Ti-6Al-4V coupons were processed using a PX200-3-GF (Edgewave GmbH, Germany) laser source emitting 12 ps pulses, also at a wavelength of 1064 nm. The laser beam was guided with mirrors to a similar DLIP head (ELIPSYS, SurFunction GmbH, Germany) from the experiments performed with ns pulses. The spot in this case had also an elongated geometry with an approximately elliptical shape with major and minor axis of 875 and 75 μm , respectively, and spatial period of 6.0 μm . Two laser repetition rates of 10 and 20 kHz were selected, as well as two different laser fluence levels (1.2 and 2.0 J cm^{-2}). The pulse-to-pulse overlap was varied in this case between 75% and 99.95%.

For the resulting topographies after the ns and ps-DLIP laser treatments, white light interferometry (WLI) as well as confocal microscopy (Sensofar S Neox 3D Surface profiler, Sensofar Metrology, Spain) were employed. For the surface roughness measurements, the AM-fabricated coupons were characterized using a 20 \times objective (confocal objective), providing a lateral and vertical resolutions of 0.31 μm and 8 nm, respectively, over an area of 3 \times 3 mm. A median spatial filter with a kernel size of 7 \times 7 μm was applied to the data. In case of the DLIP treated surfaces, a

50 \times objective (WLI) was used, providing a lateral and vertical resolutions of 0.50 μm and 0.1 nm, respectively. For each processed region, an area of 1.93 \times 0.50 mm was measured, and the resulting images, composed of 12 fields, were analyzed using SensoMap 7 software (Sensofar, Barcelona, Spain) to estimate the average structure depth.

In addition, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to obtain high resolution images of the processed samples. In this case, a Sigma 300 Gemini (Zeiss, Germany) microscope was utilized, under an acceleration voltage of 3 kV. In addition, electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) tests were performed using a FEI Helios NanoLab600 (Thermo-Fisher Scientific, Eindhoven, The Netherlands) detector. These measurements were performed at an acceleration voltage of 20 kV and a current of 11 nA. Cross-sections were prepared using focused ion beam (FIB) in the same dual station. To protect the surface, a platinum coating was deposited in situ using first electron beam induced deposition (EBID) and then ion beam induced deposition (IBID). The cross-section was done with FIB using an acceleration voltage of 30 kV. SEM images as well as ion-induced secondary electron images were obtained from the cross section.

Homogeneity analyses on the DLIP treated surfaces were performed from the WLI data over an area of 300 \times 300 μm at the central region of each track, using an adaptation of the Gini coefficient. The following procedure was implemented. First, the topography images were segmented into square unit cells, each with a side length corresponding to the spatial period. Next, a set of topographic attributes was calculated within each cell and the Gini coefficient was calculated across all cells. Specifically, the total structural height of the DLIP features, along with skewness (Ssk) and kurtosis (Sks), were assessed as key attributes. Skewness (Ssk) quantifies the asymmetry of the height distribution relative to the mean surface plane, whereas kurtosis (Sks) describes the sharpness of the peaks of the surface height distribution. Taken together, these parameters provide a comprehensive characterization of surface topography in terms of shape, roughness, and texture symmetry. After that, the geometrical mean of the obtained homogeneities was calculated as a measure of the global homogeneity of the structure (further referred in the article as structure homogeneity). Further information about this method can be found elsewhere.^[42]

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Laser Polishing of Ti–6Al–4V Samples

First, the LP process (see Figure 1a) was implemented on the Ti–6Al–4V coupons.

The polishing process relies on the shallow remelting of the surface by means of a high-power continuous wave laser. When the laser beam interacts with the surface, it induces localized melting of the topmost material layer. This transient molten phase, driven by surface tension, promotes material redistribution from surface peaks into adjacent valleys, thereby reducing overall roughness.^[43] The beam follows a series of adjacent 1D scan paths with a defined lateral overlap between passes. The degree of overlap, together with the scanning speed and laser power, are interdependent parameters that determine the extent and quality of surface smoothing. Accurate control of these parameters is critical, as similar energy inputs may produce distinct surface outcomes depending on the scanning strategy employed.

Exemplary WLI and SEM images presented in Figure 2 show the initial state of the material surface as well as its condition after the LP treatment.

Figure 2a,c illustrates the as-built condition of the additively manufactured Ti64 part fabricated with a BOA of 90°. The surface is characterized by partially melted powder particles, surface defects and a heterogeneous distribution of surface features, which are typical in surfaces produced by LPBF.^[44] In addition, the diameter of the observed particles ranges between 5 and 36 μm, which is in the range of the powder size distribution (with an average particle size of 33 μm) used in the AM process. Differently, after the LP treatment (in this case, using a laser power of 541 W), all the particles have been melted, and a significant reduction of the above-mentioned defects can be observed, as shown in Figure 2b,d. In addition, as observed in Figure 2b, the laser-polished sample shows

a smoother surface and exhibits a more refined microstructure, confirming the effectiveness of the LP treatment. Additional images of polishing of coupons fabricated at other BOA can be found in Figure S2 of the supporting information.

While topographical defects seem to be mitigated by the LP treatment, features resembling grain boundaries became evident on the polished surface (Figure 2d). To discard the presence of possible surface cracks, the polished surfaces were analyzed by EBSD, and a FIB cut was realized for a cross-sectional analysis of the remelted material. This is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3a shows a high-magnification image of a remelted region by the LP treatment. Different grains denoting various surface levels are visible, as is also shown in the FIB cut from Figure 3b. In addition, the BSE image from Figure 3c show that the remelted material has transformed to a different phase (α')^[45,46] with a much finer microstructure which can be explained by the rapid cooling of the material surface that was re-heated to above the β -transus temperature ($\approx 980^\circ\text{C}$ for Ti–6Al–4V, well below its melting point of 1600°C).^[47] The presence of the α' phase is confirmed by the EBSD analysis shown in Figure 3d. These findings are congruent with similar observations reported by other researchers, who attributed the generated surface features to grain boundary grooving caused by surface tension, rather than solidification cracks.^[18,45]

After these preliminary investigations, the effect of the laser power and BOA on the surface roughness (S_a) for the treated Ti–6Al–4V samples was evaluated in detail. This is shown in Figure 4 for laser powers up to $\approx 540\text{ W}$ and BOA from 0° to 120° . The dotted horizontal lines indicate the initial S_a roughness values for the different building orientations, ranging from $\approx 9\ \mu\text{m}$ (for BOA of 90°) to $31\ \mu\text{m}$ (for 30°).

The results demonstrate also a significant reduction in S_a values across all laser power levels compared to the initial roughness, indicating the successful reduction of surface irregularities by the LP

Figure 2. Confocal and scanning electron microscope images of a,c) as-built and b,d) laser-polished Ti–6Al–4V coupons, respectively.

Figure 3. a) SEM image and b) FIB cut of the Ti-6Al-4 V coupon surface, laser-polished at 541 W. c) BSE image of the polished surface and d) EBSD phase analysis.

Figure 4. Sa roughness as function of the applied laser power for the LP treatment as well as the BOA employed in the AM process of the Ti-6Al-4 V coupons. The dotted lines indicate initial roughness state for each BOA (see legend).

treatment. The surface roughness decreases with increasing laser power for all orientations up to a laser power of 487 W, achieving Sa values between 1.5 μm and 10 μm at this power level. As the power was increased to the highest value of 510 W, the Sa remained approximately constant, i.e., within the error bars. Furthermore, it can be seen that the BOA significantly influences the initial surface roughness of additively manufactured components. Notably a BOA of 90° resulted in a significant low Sa, highlighting its impact on surface finish. The role of building

orientation on surface characteristics has been already widely explored in previous studies. In particular, it has been reported that different build angles expose each newly deposited layer to different thermal histories, leading to variations in heat flow conditions, local solidification behavior, and remelting phenomena. These variations affect the as-built surface morphologies, including roughness levels, surface waviness, and so-called “staircase” effects, while also influencing geometric accuracy and defect formation.^[41,48–50]

These investigations permitted the identification of the most favorable BOAs for the manufacturing of the Ti-alloy parts as well as the required laser power needed to achieve roughness levels below ≈2 μm. The polished coupons with the lowest roughness levels were used for the ps-DLIP treatments, while the rougher ones were reserved for the ns treatment due to its inherent capability to further smooth the surfaces.^[51]

3.2. Direct Laser Interference Patterning with ns Pulses

The DLIP process using nanosecond pulses was implemented to fabricate line-like structures over the laser-polished Ti-6Al-4V samples with a spatial period of 6.0 μm. Exemplary images (confocal and SEM) of samples treated with different process parameters are shown in **Figure 5**. When using nanosecond pulses (7 ns), structure formation is dominated by thermal mechanisms. The periodic topography results from two distinct processes. First, transient melting occurs at interference maxima. Then, as the melt depth increases the melt expulsion process begins generating radial displacement of molten material toward interference minima positions. At lower fluence levels, the mechanism responsible for the redistribution of molten material is the surface-tension gradient induced by the lateral variation of the temperature, also

Figure 5. Line-like periodic patterns produced using ns-DLIP (7 ns) at 2.8 J cm^{-2} and 5 kHz in Ti-6Al-4 V laser-polished coupons (laser power: 487 W, BOA: 30°) with a pulse-to-pulse overlap of: a,b) 60%, c,d) 95%, and e,f) 99%. (a,c,e) WLI images; (b,d,e) SEM images.

known as Marangoni convection.^[52,53] At higher laser fluences, the recoil pressure induced by the evaporated material over the molten areas dominates the pattern formation process.^[54] Adjusting the cumulated laser fluence by varying the pulse-to-pulse overlap allows controlling the structure's topography. For example, when processing the samples at a repetition rate of 5 kHz and a laser fluence of 2.8 J cm^{-2} , a relatively low overlap of 60% produced shallow structures (below $2.0 \mu\text{m}$) as shown in in Figure 5a,b. From Figure 5b it can be also appreciated that the structures produced at this overlap (60%) show well-defined ridges (located at the interference minima positions) at the central region of the laser spot. However, in the surrounding areas (top and bottom of Figure 5b) a double-peak structure is observed since the applied laser fluence was not enough to fully displace the molten material from the interference maxima to the minima.^[55]

This effect can be avoided when increasing the pulse-to-pulse overlap (or increasing the cumulated laser fluence), e.g., up to 95%, as shown in Figure 5c,d. Thus, in all regions the applied laser fluence was high enough to form homogenous and parallel ridges. The structure depth of the pattern was in this case $\approx 6.0 \mu\text{m}$, corresponding to an aspect ratio (AR, quotient between the structure depth and the spatial period) of 1.^[55,56] Further increasing the

overlap up to 99% led to a decrease in the quality of the line-like features (see Figure 5e,f) due to the significantly high energy density deposited on the surface, as already reported by other authors.^[26,57]

The evolution of the structure depth with the used pulse-to-pulse overlap is shown in Figure 6a, for the coupon fabricated with a BOA of 30° and treated with repetition rates of 1.5 and 5 kHz. It is important to note that the laser power was adjusted to maintain a constant laser fluence per pulse (2.8 J cm^{-2}) at both repetition rates. Consequently, for a given overlap, the surfaces received the same cumulative laser fluence, independently of the used frequency. Clearly, a significant difference can be observed in the reached structure depths depending on the used repetition rates. At 5 kHz, the produced structures were deeper than at 1.5 kHz, for overlaps up to 95%. In addition, the patterns produced at 5 kHz also had the highest homogeneity as revealed by the Gini analysis shown in Figure 6b and the length of the error bars in Figure 6a. In particular, homogeneity levels up to 87.5% could be achieved for the surface treated with an overlap of 90%, reaching a structure depth of $4.7 \mu\text{m}$.

The reason for the significantly deeper structures at the highest repetition rate can be explained by heat accumulation effects.

Figure 6. a,c) Structure depth and b,d) surface homogeneity as a function of pulse-to-pulse OV for laser-polished Ti64 coupons. For the results shown in (a) and (b), the Ti64 samples were produced with a BOA of 30° and polished at 487 W. In case of figures (c) and (d), the BOA was 0° and the samples were polished at 487 W. For the DLIP treatment, the used laser wavelength was 1064 nm, and the pulse duration 7 ns.

For instance, Lang et al.^[58] showed similar effects on stainless steel surfaces treated also with ns-DLIP, attributing the deeper structures to the reduction of the energy density required to remelt the material due to heat accumulation processes caused at high repetition rates. These findings were confirmed by numerical calculations using the algorithm developed by Weber et al.^[57] Similar results were observed for other BOA, as shown in Figure 6c,d for 0°.

3.3. Direct Laser Interference Patterning with ps Pulses

The use of picosecond pulses in combination with DLIP withholds several benefits being the most noticeable of all the reduction of the heat-affected zone (HAZ) and thus reducing possible modifications of the bulk material due to the thermal process (e.g., induced by heat accumulation).

In this case, the laser-polished Ti64 surfaces were irradiated at different pulse-to-pulse overlaps as well as laser fluences resulting in very different surface patterns. Exemplary images of the treated surfaces are shown in **Figure 7**.

Figure 7a,b show the typical obtained topography for this material when using low overlaps (80%). As it can be seen, the produced line-like structures have a low structure depth ($\approx 0.6 \mu\text{m}$) and in addition to the line-like features produced by the local ablation of material at the interference maxima positions, also LIPSS could be observed. The produced LIPSS have an orientation

perpendicular to the DLIP features as well as to the used beam polarization, which is characteristic of the low spatial frequency LIPSS (LSFL).^[59] In addition, the spatial period of the LIPSS features was calculated from 2D fast Fourier transforms (2D-FFT), delivering an approximate value of 900 nm, which is similar to but lower than the used laser wavelength. This property is also a common characteristic of LSFL (see Figure S3 in Supporting Information).^[60,61]

Increasing the overlap up to 95% produced deeper structures, reaching a structure depth of 2.9 μm , which approaches an AR of 0.5, which is typical for metals irradiated at similar conditions (see Figures 7c,d).^[29,62] Also in this case, the LSFL can be observed but they are less prominent (the analysis of additional DLIP patterns having LSFL is further investigated in Figure S3, in the Supporting Information section). For samples treated with overlaps exceeding 99%, the structures were significantly damaged (similar to ns-DLIP-treated surfaces) due to excessively high energy densities deposited on the surfaces. This led to the formation of a texture with random peaks and valleys (see Figures 7e,f) and without long-range order. Furthermore, LIPSS features were not visible in this case. Additional images of DLIP textured surfaces over coupons processed using different polishing parameters can be found in Figure S4 and S5 of the supporting information.

Following, the influence of the process parameters on the structure depth was further analyzed. **Figure 8** shows the average structure depth of the DLIP line-like structures as function of the

Figure 7. Line-like periodic patterns produced using ps-DLIP at 2.0 J cm^{-2} of laser fluence and a repetition rate of 10 kHz in Ti64. The used pulse-to-pulse overlaps were: a,b) 80%, c,d) 95%, and e,f) 99.95%. (a,c,e) WLI images; (b,d,e) SEM images. The samples were produced with a BOA of 90° and polished at 541 W.

pulse-to-pulse overlap (OV%), for samples produced with BOA angles of 90° and 120° , which were previously polished at 325 W (Figures 8a,b), 433 W (Figures 8c,d), and 541 W (Figures 8e,f). In general, the structure depth increased (as well as the AR) as function of the pulse-to-pulse overlap for all used fluences (1.2 and 2.0 J cm^{-2}) and repetition rates (10 and 20 kHz). For overlaps below 95%, the measured structure depths along the irradiated area showed lower variations than at $\text{OV} = 99\%$ which is denoted by the length of error bars. For the highest overlaps (95%–99%), deeper structures could be fabricated, although characterized by a significant increment of the standard deviation, suggesting a degradation of the texture homogeneity. Further increasing the overlap ($>99\%$) led to the total destruction of the line-like pattern, and thus these measurements were not included in the figure.

The results showed in Figure 8 also denote that neither the used repetition rates (10 and 20 kHz) nor the BOAs affect the reached structure depths. The first can be explained by the lower induced HAZ, which is typical in picosecond ablation processes of metals, where the irradiated material is primarily ablated rather than melted.^[63]

In this case, the effect observed for ns-DLIP, where an increase in repetition rate promoted structure growth through heat accumulation, was not detected. As it can be seen in Figure 8, for the ps pulses, increasing the repetition rate from 10 to 20 kHz had a negligible influence on the final structure depth, despite these frequencies being up to four times higher than those employed for the ns-DLIP treatment. To demonstrate the influence of pulse duration on heat accumulation, the model developed by Weber et al. was adapted to calculate the thermal evolution in ns- and ps-DLIP treated samples, using Equation (1)^[57]

$$T_{\text{Sum}, nD}(t) = \frac{Q_{nD}}{\rho c_p \sqrt{4\pi k}} \sum_{N=1}^{N_p} \frac{\Theta\left(t - \frac{N-1}{f_L}\right)}{\sqrt{\left(t - \frac{N-1}{f_L}\right)^{nD}}} e^{-\left(\frac{1}{t - \frac{N-1}{f_L}}\right)^{\frac{r_{nD}^2}{4k}}} \quad (1)$$

here Q_{nD} is the residual heat introduced into the material, ρ is the density of the material, c_p its specific heat capacity, $k = \lambda_{\text{th}} (\rho c_p)^{-1}$ is the diffusivity, λ_{th} the heat conductivity, t is time, r the spatial coordinate, f_L the laser repetition rate, and N_p the number of

Figure 8. Structure depth as function of the pulse-to-pulse OV for ps-DLIP treatment of Ti64-AM samples with BOA of a,c,e) 90° and b,d,f) 120°. The applied laser power for the polishing process were: (a,b) 325, (c,d) 433, and (e,f) 541 W. For the DLIP treatment, the used laser wavelength was 1064 nm, and the pulse duration 12 ps.

pulses. The solution of the 1D heat flow can be assumed due to the large elliptical shape of the laser spot, which gives $N_D = 1$ for the dimension indicator. For the calculations, a fluence of 2.0 J cm^{-2} and a repetition rate of 20 kHz was used for the ps-DLIP treatment, and 2.8 J cm^{-2} and 5 kHz for the ns pulses. In both cases, 100 pulses were simulated, corresponding to an overlap of 99%. The most important difference between both pulse regimes lays in the calculation of the residual heat $Q_{r,D}$. For ultrashort laser pulses irradiating metallic materials, the residual fraction of heat left in the workpiece is can be assumed to be around 0.2 times the incident energy as indicated by Finger et al. in previous works.^[64] In contrast, based on a previous study from Lang et al., for ns pulses this fraction can be estimated close to unity since the amount of vaporized material is very low.^[58] The calculated temperature evolutions can be found in Figure S5 of the Supporting Information. It can be observed that the use of ns pulses produces an increase of 740 K after 100 pulses at 5 kHz whereas ps-treatment only elevated the temperature 207 K at a repetition rate of 20 KHz. These findings are in line with early reports that addressed heat accumulation effects at much higher frequencies for ps laser sources (in the MHz range).^[65,66]

Additionally, the results show no significant difference in structure depth for samples treated at different laser fluences (1.2 and 2.0 J cm^{-2}), which indicates that similar structural morphologies can be achieved with lower energy input, contributing to the sustainability of the process.

The homogeneity of the produced surface topographies was also quantified using Gini coefficient (as for the Ti-6Al-4V samples treated with the 7 ns pulses). **Figure 9** summarizes the calculated values from the Gini analysis regarding the structural

Figure 9. Structure homogeneity of the line-like produced patterns by ps-DLIP as function of the pulse-to-pulse overlap for a Ti64 sample fabricated at a BOA of 90° and polished with 541 W.

homogeneity of the sample built with a BOA of 90° and polished at 541 W of laser power. This sample serves as a representative example for the entire tested batch, which included samples with different BOAs. From the diagram it can be seen that the main factor influencing the calculated homogeneity is the overlap and that the homogeneity increases with this parameter up to 89%-91% for $OV = 92.5\%$. A further increase in overlap leads to a rapid deterioration of the structure's periodicity (as previously shown in Figures 7e,f) due to the high cumulated laser fluence.

3.4. Cost-Effectiveness Analysis for Optimizing Process Parameters and Surface Quality

To optimize DLIP on laser-polished Ti-6Al-4V (Ti64) fabricated by AM, a structured evaluation method was developed, balancing both energy consumption and surface characteristics. This approach enables the identification of optimal process

Table 1. Initial values of cost function coefficients.

Coefficient	Value
w_{AR}	30
AR_{target}	0.5
k_{AR}	1
w_{Fcum}	15
k_{Fcum}	1000
w_{Fpcum}	15
k_{Fpcum}	20 000
w_H	25
H_t	1
k_H	2
w_{pol}	15
k_{pol}	1
Sa target [μm]	0.5

Figure 10. a) Calculated cost function for the different process parameters (n test) used in this study, for both ns and ps-DLIP treatments. WLI images of the structures that yielded the lowest and highest cost function values for b,c) ps-DLIP and d,e) ns-DLIP.

Table 2. Process parameters needed to reach the lowest cost values for both ns and ps-DLIP treatments (* BOA: 120°; ** BOA: 0°).

DLIP	Cost value [a.u.]	AR	Structure depth [μm]	OV [%]	Cumulated fluence $_{\text{DLIP}}$ [J cm^{-2}]	Polishing power [W]	Homogeneity [a.u.]	Initial roughness [μm]
ps	24.01	≈ 0.48	2.9	95	42	325	0.89	5.2*
ns	20.25	≈ 0.9	5.4	90	28	325	0.94	17.1**

parameters that maximize performance while maintaining cost-effectiveness.

A rational cost function was designed to systematically compare and rank different experimental runs by inputting the process parameter in the function equation. This method ensures interpretability while preventing excessive penalties due to parameter variations. Traditional exponential or linear cost models often suffer from either uncontrolled growth or insensitivity in complex processes.^[67] In contrast, the rational cost function used here provides controlled scaling, allowing multiple parameters with different magnitudes to be integrated into a single, meaningful metric.

Equation (2) defines the cost function, incorporating five key parameters that influence both polishing and DLIP treatments considering topographical target parameters

$$Cf = w_{AR} \frac{AR_{target}}{k_{AR} + AR} + w_{F_{cum}} \frac{F_{cum}}{k_{F_{cum}} + F_{cum}} + w_{F_{pcum}} \frac{F_{pcum}}{k_{F_{pcum}} + F_{pcum}} + w_H \frac{|H - Ht|}{k_H + |H - Ht|} + w_{pol} \frac{Sa_{target}}{k_{pol} + Sa} \quad (2)$$

Each individual term takes the general form of $C_i = w_i \cdot x_i / (k_i + x_i)$, ensuring that the parameter x_i grows the cost in a smooth manner, saturating at a maximum value given by the weight (w_i). Based on previous experiences from our research team, the selected process parameters considered for this study were: AR of the DLIP structures, the cumulated fluence (F_{cum}) used for the DLIP treatment, the cumulated fluence for the polishing process (F_{pcum}), structure homogeneity (H) of the DLIP features and the surface roughness parameter Sa obtained after the polishing treatment.

This cost function provides a flexible framework where parameters can be adjusted based on specific experimental goals (e.g., a target AR).^[68] The equation favors lower amounts of applied energy (cumulative laser fluence) for the polish and DLIP processes combined with higher ARs, as the objective was to achieve the deepest possible structures while minimizing energy consumption.

Following this idea, the coefficients listed in Table 1 were used for the calculation of the cost function given by Equation (2).

Figure 10a presents the resulting cost function values for the experiments performed in this study. The optimum processing conditions that minimize the cost function for both the ps (blue dots) and ns-DLIP treatments (black dots) are listed in Table 2. WLI images of the structures that yielded both the lowest and highest cost for each pulse duration are highlighted also in the figure. Namely, in Figure 10b,d surfaces with a well-defined and homogeneous structure can be appreciated for pulse durations in the ps and ns regimes, respectively. In Figure 10c,e, surfaces with severe over melting are shown for ps and ns pulses, respectively. These

exemplary topography images serve to illustrate the capability of the employed equation to identify a suitable process window. Furthermore, while for the Ti64 samples treated with ps pulses, the lowest value of the cost function was ≈ 24 , for the ns treatment this value could be further reduced to 20 ($\approx 17\%$ reduction).

This behavior is primarily due to the significantly deeper structures produced by ns pulses, as the molten material at the maxima positions contributes to the overall structure depth. Additionally, in the ns-DLIP treatment, structures formed at higher repetition rates exhibited lower costs, as the cumulative heat deposition allowed for larger depths.

4. Conclusions

In this work, a two-step laser-based process was developed for the sustainable surface treatment of Ti-6Al-4 V components. This concept implemented the combination of LP (using a CW laser source) as well as DLIP with ns and ps pulses. The key findings of this study are as follows. 1) In the process of fabrication of the Ti-6Al-4V coupons by LPBF, it was found that the building orientation angle had a significant influence on the resulting initial surface roughness, being the lowest $9 \mu\text{m}$ for a BOA of 90° and the highest $31 \mu\text{m}$ for 30° . 2) The LP treatment successfully reduced the surface roughness up to a factor of 7.5 (e.g., from 19.1 to $2.5 \mu\text{m}$), depending on the initial surface roughness value. 3) For the DLIP treatment with ns pulses, it was found that an increase in the pulse-to-pulse overlap initially led to an increase in structure depth (up to $7.1 \mu\text{m}$) followed by a degradation of the periodic structure for overlaps greater than 99%. In addition, the repetition rate also influenced the process of structure formation for the ns-DLIP treatment, due to heat accumulation. Homogeneities up to 94 % could be reached, for the sample with a BOA = 0° , polished with 325 W and treated at 2.8 J cm^{-2} and 5 kHz. 4) Additionally, the use of ultrashort pulses (ps-DLIP) enabled the fabrication of hierarchical surface patterns by combining LIPSS with the DLIP features in a single step. In case of the ps-DLIP treatment, higher overlaps resulted in deeper line-like structures up to $4.4 \mu\text{m}$ at 99% overlap. For overlaps greater than 99%, a degradation of the periodic structures was observed. The best homogeneities reached with the ps-DLIP treatment were 92 % for the samples treated at with a BOA 120° , polished with 541 W and treated at 2.0 J cm^{-2} and 10 kHz. Furthermore, neither the BOAs or LP conditions affected significantly the DLIP treatment. 5) Finally, a novel cost function was developed to determine the most appropriate process parameters for enhancing the sustainability of the process (low energy consumption) for reaching a target AR of structures. In general, it was observed that the ns processing resulted in lower cost function than ps-DLIP treatment, mostly due to the significantly deeper structures obtained for similar cumulated laser fluences.

Although the study does not address specific functional applications, the insights gained will enable the sustainable production of functional 3D parts in future work.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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additive manufacturing, cost function, direct laser interference patterning, laser polishing, sustainable processing

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